

Chemical Reactivity and Light Absorption. Part III.

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In previous publications of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 33, 311) it has been shown that the light absorption by a mixture of two reacting substances is greater than the absorptions of the reacting substances considered separately. This reaction is found to be applicable to numerous chemical reactions. It seems that whenever there is a possibility of the occurrence of a chemical change by mixing two or more substances, increased light absorption by the mixture is likely to be observed.

Further work has been carried out on this line with reactions involving iodine and the results are recorded in this paper.

Iodine and Acetone.

It has been shown in Part II (*loc. cit.*) that the light absorption by a mixture of acetone and iodine is greater than the absorptions of acetone and iodine taken separately. We have studied this reaction further in different spectral regions and it will be observed from the following photographs that there is increased light absorption in the ultraviolet and visible regions with the mixture, but so far we have not been able to detect any enhanced absorption in the infra-red region. In this reaction hydrochloric acid is added to accelerate the reaction.

The photograph as shown in Fig. 2 was taken with a light filter in order to isolate some particular spectral regions. One quartz cell contained a saturated solution of cobalt chloride and the other 0.06% of K_2CrO_4 solution. These filters were placed next to the source of light and then the reaction vessel. The light coming out of these was photographed (Fig. 2).

Photographs were also taken with a E_1 type of quartz spectrograph and one of them is submitted here (*cf.* Fig. 1).

Infra-red Absorption.

In order to study the light absorption in the near infra-red, ordinary photographic plates were sensitised.

The following sensitising solution was prepared: water-alcohol mixture (85:60) 150 c.c., neocyanin solution (1:2000 in absolute alcohol) 1.5 c.c., kryptocyanin solution (1:1000 in absolute alcohol) 2 c.c., dicyanin solution (1:100 in absolute alcohol) 2.5 c.c. To this solution was added concentrated ammonia (5.5 c.c.), all these mixings being carried on in the dark. Ilford Empress plates were dipped in the above solution for 5 minutes and then rinsed for $\frac{1}{2}$ minute in alcohol and rapidly dried before a fan.

The plates thus sensitised showed lines up to 9500\AA but require long exposure. In our experiments, long exposures could not be given as the products of the reaction might take part in the light absorption. Hence, lines up to 8000\AA could only be obtained with these plates after an exposure lasting for 45 seconds. Photographs were taken in an Adam Hilger constant deviation glass spectrophotometer. The lines were standardised from a standard emission spectrum of copper arc in Eder's Atlas.

The photograph as given in Fig. 3 shows the light absorption by sodium nitrite solution and aqueous iodine and their mixtures in the infra-red region. Similar results were obtained with acetone and iodine.

As there are no strong lines in the region of 7000\AA with copper arc as the source of light, it is difficult to say whether any absorption takes place in that region. But this can be said with a certain amount of definiteness that no absorption takes place at 8000\AA .

It is well known that the absorption spectra of iodine vapour consists of a band system extending from the red to the green. There is also a much weaker band system in the near infra-red with a maximum at 7300\AA . Another set of bands occurs in the ultraviolet between 2750 to 1700\AA . The photographs as given in Fig. 1-4 show that aqueous iodine has absorption in the region 4500 to 5000\AA and again selective absorption in the ultraviolet after 3194\AA , but no appreciable absorption has been observed in the near infra-red.

Aqueous iodine and potassium oxalate, sodium nitrite, sodium citrate, sodium tartrate and sodium lactate.—A few photographs with concentrated solutions of the above reducing agents and aqueous iodine were taken with a E_1 Hilger quartz

spectrograph with copper arc as the light source. All the photographs show markedly increased absorption in visible and ultra-violet regions with the mixtures of iodine and the reducing agent in comparison with the two reacting substances considered separately. One of the typical photographs is reproduced in Fig. 4.

*Relation between Velocity of Thermal Reaction and
Light Absorption.*

In Part II of this series, it has been stated that under comparable conditions, those reactions, which are fast show greater light absorption with mixtures than in the case of reactions which are slow.

In order to obtain exactly comparable results, we have determined the light absorptions with mixtures containing $M/5$ solutions of the reducing agents and $N/437$ aqueous iodine and the comparative velocities of the reactions in the dark have also been measured by mixing 25 c.c. of each of the solution of the reducing agent and 25 c.c. of the same aqueous iodine at 25° and titrating with a standard sodium thiosulphate solution. Two of the photographs showing increased light absorption by the mixtures, are reproduced in Figs. 5 and 6.

In Table I the increased light absorption by mixtures of the reducing agents and iodine and the comparative velocities of the reactions in the dark at 25° are recorded.

TABLE I.

Reactants.	Amount of increased absorption.	$N/2371.2$ thio consumed after 6'. (Dark velocity in decreasing order)
1. Hydrazine sulphate (2 c.c.) + conc. HCl	Almost nil	Extremely rapid
1. Hypophosphorous acid	$23\overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$	5.7 c.c. (in 3'.)
2. Sodium formate	73	4.9
4. Ferrous sulphate	860	2.95
5. Sodium malonate	73	1.6
6. Sodium nitrite	1605	1.3
7. Sodium citrate	248	0.95
8. Sodium lactate	73	0.9
9. Sodium malate	877	0.8
10. Acetone	513	0.6
11. Sodium tartrate	73	0.6
12. Phosphorous acid	Almost nil	Nil
13. Potassium oxalate	$513 \overset{\circ}{\text{A}}$	Nil

The right column shows the amount of sodium thiosulphate consumed in 6 minutes in decreasing order, *i.e.*, the order of the dark velocity of the reaction between the reducing agents and iodine. The central column gives the amount of increased light absorption with mixtures of reducing agents and iodine under identical condition.

From the above table we find that the dark velocity of the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine is practically nil in 6 minutes, but the amount of increased light absorption is 513\AA , and the dark velocity of the reaction between sodium formate and iodine is fairly high but the increased light absorption is only 73\AA . Similarly the velocity of reaction between hypophosphorous acid and iodine is great but the absorption is as low as 23\AA .

Hence, it can be stated that no quantitative relation exists between the dark velocity of reaction and the amount of increased absorption.

Relation between the Heat of Reaction and Amount of Increased Light Absorption.

In order to study how the binding forces of the molecules of iodine are weakened by the presence of reducing agents, the heat of the reaction between the reducing agents and iodine solution was determined.

Experimental procedure.—The heat of the reaction was estimated calorimetrically, a highly polished silver calorimeter being used. The calorimeter was placed in an air-jacket, and the whole apparatus was enclosed in a wooden box and the experimental room was closed on all sides in order to avoid a draft and thus ensuring against external temperature variations. A Beckmann thermometer was used to note the temperature. The reacting solutions were placed in a thermostat so that the temperatures of both the solutions were constant. The calorimeter was tested by putting in 50 c.c. of water in it and noting the temperature at intervals. It was found that the temperature remained constant for 5 hours. 25 C.c. of the reactants were put in the calorimeter and the temperature of the mixture noted after stirring well. The rise in temperature of the mixture was noted at regular intervals until the temperature of the mixture was constant. Each experiment was repeated and the mean of the two results is recorded. 25 C.c. of each solution were mixed in all cases. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II.

Heat of reaction between reducing agents and iodine solutions.

Composition of the mixtures.	Initial temp.	Final temp.	Period to attain final temp.	Heat of reaction per g. atom of I ₂ .
<i>M</i> -NaNO ₂ + <i>N</i> /326·4-I ₂	1·29°	2·70°	7½ hr.	1,073,856 Cal.
<i>M</i> /5-FeSO ₄ + <i>N</i> /61·35-I ₂	2·84°	4·64°	5½	257,904
<i>M</i> /5-Na-formate + <i>N</i> /65·8-I ₂	1·1°	1·61°	4½	78,702
<i>M</i> /H ₃ PO ₂ + <i>N</i> /62·8-I ₂	1·45°	1·595°	¾	21,226·4

TABLE III

Reducing agents.	Amount of increased absorption with mol. conc. of reactants.	Heat of reaction.
Hypophosphorous acid	23 Å	21,226·4 Cal.
Sodium formate	73	78,702·0
Ferrous sulphate	860	257,904·0
Sodium nitrite	1606	1,073,856·0

The order of increased light absorption is NaNO₂ > FeSO₄ > H·CO₂Na > H₃PO₂; and the heat of reaction follows the same order. Moreover, it has been calculated from thermochemical data by Dhar and Bhattacharya that the heats of the reactions of potassium oxalate and halogens are as follows: K₂C₂O₄ + Cl₂, 84 Cal; K₂C₂O₄ + Br₂, 62 Cal; K₂C₂O₄ + I₂, 32 Cal; and their light absorptions also follow the same order, *viz.*, the absorption due to K₂C₂O₄ + Cl₂ is the maximum, then comes K₂C₂O₄ + Br₂ and lastly K₂C₂O₄ + I₂.

It appears, therefore, that the greater the heat of a reaction, the greater is the chance of the loosening of the binding forces of the molecules and consequent increased light absorption.

SUMMARY.

1. Increased light absorption for mixtures have been observed in the ultraviolet, and visible regions but not in the infra-red region, with several reactions involving aqueous iodine.

5. The increased light absorption is due to activation of molecules which is associated with the weakening of the binding forces of the molecules.

3. No quantitative relation exists between the velocity of a reaction in the dark and increased light absorption.

4. It appears that the heat of the reaction and increased light absorption by mixtures go hand in hand.

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FIG. 1.
Visible and ultraviolet region (3191Å—5220Å),

- Exposure—30 sec.
- 1. Copper arc. 2. 20 c.c. N/700-I₂. 3. 20 c.c. 2% acetone. 4. N/350-I₂ + 4% acetone. 5. 20 c.c. 1.25% acetone.
 - 6. 2.5% acetone + N/350-I₂. 7. 20 c.c. 0.7% acetone. 8. 1% acetone + N/350-I₂. 9. 20 c.c. N/1400-I₂
 - 10. N/700-I₂ + 4% acetone. 11. 20 c.c. N/1400-I₂ + 2.5% acetone. 12. N/700-I₂ + 2.5% acetone.

FIG. 2. Range of transmission (3290—2961Å) ; mean 3125Å.

Exposure—30 sec.

1. Copper arc
2. 20 c.c. 2% acetone (3100Å)
3. 20 c.c. N/700—I₂ (3100Å)
4. 4% acetone + N/350—I₂ (total absorption) 3247Å
5. 20 c.c. 1.25% acetone (2961Å) 3266
6. 2.5% acetone + N/350—I₂ (3274Å)
7. 0.25% acetone (2961Å)
8. 0.5% acetone + N/350 I₂ (3150Å)

FIG. 3.

5218Å 5700Å 6125Å 8000Å

Exposure—30 sec.

1. Cu—arc.
2. 20 c.c. N/700-aq. I₂
3. 20 c.c. N/2—NaNO₂
4. 20 c.c. N—NaNO₂ + N/350-aq. I₂.

FIG. 4.

1 2 3 4

5105
5220

- 1) Cu-arc. 2) 20 c.c. N/800-aq. I₂ (selective absorption). 3) 20 c.c. N-K₂C₂O₄ (slight selective absorption). 4) N/400-aq. I₂ + 2N—K₂C₂O₄ (4022Å and selective absorption in visible region).

FIG. 5.

$N/5\text{-NaNO}_2 + N/437\text{-aq. I}_2$ (exposure—10 sec.).

1. Cu-arc. 2. 20 c.c. $N/874\text{-aq. I}_2(2370\text{\AA})$. 3. 20 c.c. $M/10\text{-NaNO}_2(2576\text{\AA})$. 4. $N/437\text{-aq. I}_2 + M/5\text{-NaNO}_2(3975\text{\AA})$.
 5. 20 c.c. $M/20\text{-NaNO}_2$. 6. $M/10\text{-NaNO}_2 + N/437\text{ aq. I}_2$.
 7. 20 c.c. $N/1748\text{-aq. I}_2$. 8. $N/874\text{-aq. I}_2 + M/5\text{-NaNO}_2$.

Increase in absorption $(3975 - 2370)\text{\AA} = 1605\text{\AA}$

FIG. 6.

$M/5\text{-FeSO}_4 + \text{aq. I}_2 - N/437$ (exposure—10 sec.).

- Cu-arc
 20 c.c. $N/894\text{-aq. I}_2$
 (2370 \AA)
 20 c.c. $-M/10\text{-FeSO}_4$
 (2618 \AA)
 $N/437\text{-aq. I}_2 + M/5\text{-FeSO}_4$ (3230 \AA)
 20 c.c. $M/20\text{-FeSO}_4$
 $M/10\text{-FeSO}_4 + N/437\text{-aq. I}_2$
 20 c.c. $N/1748\text{-aq. I}_2$
 $M/5\text{-FeSO}_4 + N/874\text{-aq. I}_2$

Increase in absorption $(3230 - 2375)\text{\AA} = 860\text{\AA}$

